

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/314368303>

Participation of Women in Zimbabwean Politics and the Mirage of Gender Equity

Article · January 2015

CITATION

1

READS

7,375

3 authors:

Mandlenkosi Maphosa

National University of Science and Technology, Bulawayo

9 PUBLICATIONS 10 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Nevel Tshuma

National University of Science and Technology, Bulawayo

8 PUBLICATIONS 8 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Gracious Ncube

University of the Witwatersrand

8 PUBLICATIONS 22 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Project

international trends in development [View project](#)

Project

Transnational migration and families in Tsholotsho [View project](#)

Special Issue: Elites, Institutions and Socioeconomic Inequalities in Africa

Participation of Women in Zimbabwean Politics and the Mirage of Gender Equity

Mandlenkosi Maphosa

*Institute of Development Studies, National University of
Science and Technology, Zimbabwe.*

phosaꜛ@gmail.com

Nevel Tshuma

*Institute of Development Studies, National University of
Science and Technology, Zimbabwe*

tshumeꜛ@gmail.com

Gracious Maviza

*Institute of Development Studies, National University of
Science and Technology, Zimbabwe*

graencube@gmail.com

Abstract

Zimbabwe has signed and ratified a number of regional and international instruments that call for gender equality in various spheres of life. However, in spite of the existence of these supportive instruments, the country has not fared well in advancing the participation of women in politics. The Southern African Development Community (SADC) Gender and Development barometer reveals that whilst women participation in politics is still below agreed benchmarks, Zimbabwe's citizens seem to believe the country is doing well in that regard. This article argues that the discrepancy between the perceived and actual realities in relation to the participation of women in politics is not by accident but is founded

on a systemic and calculated maneuver by politically dominant males to open up the political space when necessary and convenient for them. We argue, drawing examples from different political players, that the participation of women in politics has been more of manipulation than a genuine attempt to promote gender equality and equity. The article argues that whilst there have been some moves to bring about parity in numeric terms, there is a glass ceiling for women in terms of how far they can go up the political ladder. It is in this vein that we hypothesize that women have been sold a political dummy where through a raft of cosmetic measures they have been given an impression that they are equals in governance yet on the other hand recent political developments reveal that gender equity in governance remains a mirage for them.

Keywords: *Women, Gender equity, Gender equality, Politics, Zimbabwe*

Introduction

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) articles 2 and 21 state that everyone has a right to partake in the government of his/her country without discrimination on the basis of sex (United Nations, 2015). Furthermore, female representation and participation in political processes alongside violence against women and women's land rights are the three focus areas of the African Women's Rights Observatory (UNECA, 2012). In the regional sphere, the SADC Gender Protocol in article 12, paragraph 1, calls for a 50% threshold of women in decision making positions (SADC, 2008). Locally, the 2013 Zimbabwean constitution stipulates that women should have equal opportunities as those of men in all spheres including in political participation (Government of Zimbabwe, 2013). In spite of the existence of these supportive instruments, Zimbabwe has not fared well in advancing the participation of women in governance. The SADC Gender and Development Index highlights that Zimbabwe is at a 41% threshold of achieving set targets relating to the participation of women in governance. Furthermore, the SADC Citizen Score Card puts the Zimbabwean citizens' perceptions of their governments' commitment to gender in governance at the 61% threshold (Morna *et al.*, 2014).

This article argues that the discrepancy between the perceived and actual realities in relation to the participation of women in politics is not by accident but is founded on a systemic and calculated manoeuvre by politically dominant males to open up the political space when necessary and convenient for them. Thus the premise of the article is that the citizens' perceptions are shaped by the images and gestures projected by the ruling male elite on issues of gender equality in politics. These elites have for a long time projected an image of being gender sensitive by mainly signing and domesticating a number of international and regional gender related legal instruments. However, a close analysis of how male political figures have been (ab)using women to further their political ends compels one to argue that these gestures of being gender sensitive have been nothing but a ruse since in spite of signing the various legal instruments they have been simultaneously putting a glass ceiling on women's path towards greater political participation. A typical example of this behavior can be deciphered from an excerpt of a speech attributed to President Robert Mugabe (commenting on the then Zimbabwean Vice President Joice Mujuru's purported political ambitions) who said: We are experiencing it for the first time in ZANU-PF and for that matter it's a woman who is saying, 'I want to take over that seat' (quoted in *Reuters*, 2014).

The fact that the President said "for that matter it's a woman..." betrays all the efforts his government has made in an effort to bring about gender equality in political participation. It can be inferred from the speech that the President and by extension the governments that he has presided over for 35 years do not believe in the equality of men and women. The purpose of this article is to discuss the position of women in Zimbabwe's political processes specifically pointing out how the fortunes and misfortunes of women in politics are intertwined to men's political interests. Whilst there is a wealth of literature on the

participation of women in governance in Zimbabwe (see Kurebwa, 2014; Dube, 2013; Kwangwari, 2014 amongst others) there is dearth of literature that analyses how initiatives created purportedly to advance the participation of women in politics are (ab)used by men to further their political interests. This article fills this lacuna. It argues that the participation of women in governance has been more of what Aviel (1981:157) called “a mere practice of embellishment”. The article highlights that whilst there have been some moves in terms of women ascending to some influential positions in political governance and in efforts to bring about parity in numeric terms, there is a glass ceiling for women when it comes to how far they can climb the political ladder. It is in this vein that we hypothesize that women have been sold a political dummy where through a raft of cosmetic measures they have been given an impression that they are equals in governance. Recent events typified by Mugabe’s 2014 statement reveal that gender equity in governance remains a mirage in Zimbabwe. Given that women are varied in terms of their interests and status, this article concentrates on key women political figures that have been or are still involved in national level party and government politics. The article is based on a desk review of literature. To get firsthand accounts from key political players, the article draws from excerpts extracted from various media publications.

Following this introduction, the paper is organised into four major sections as follows. Section two scans the international and domestic institutional environment that affect the participation of women in Zimbabwean political processes. Subsequently, section three reviews the concept of political participation. Section four assesses the participation of women in post-colonial Zimbabwean politics in three historical epochs, namely the period from 1980-2008; the period of the Government of National Unity (GNU) (2009-2013); and the post-GNU period (2013 to 2015. These

periods mark the major political milestones of the country and therefore provide a framework to examine whether the participation of women in political processes have changed or remained the same across the epochs. Finally, section five concludes the paper.

Institutional Frameworks for Gender Equality in Political Participation

The UDHR states that everyone has a right to partake in the government of his/her country. The UDHR upholds that “everyone is entitled to all the rights and freedoms set forth in this Declaration, without distinction of any kind, such as race, colour, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status”¹. Given the low numbers of women in political positions compared to men as highlighted in the foregoing, a number of measures have been taken to ensure equity and equality is upheld. As such, the UDHR has been the pedestal upon which many other statutory instruments have been crafted to strengthen and uphold the notion of human rights and ensuring equality within and between genders. Women have over time been discriminated by both prevalent beliefs and social systems that favour men in terms of opportunities for participation in the economic and socio-political spheres. This has mainly been due to cultural cleavages of patriarchy that have existed over time (Mangezvo, 2013). As a way of rectifying these incongruities, a number of international and regional declarations and/or conventions have been crafted to aid the participation of women in political processes. These include the Beijing Declaration of 1995, the Convention on the Elimination of all Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW), African Women’s Rights Observatory (AWRO) and the SADC Gender

¹ http://www.ohchr.org/EN/UDHR/Documents/UDHR_Translations/eng.pdf

Protocol, among others. All these were aimed at bringing the perceptions, experience, knowledge and interests of women as well as men to bear on policy-making, planning and decision making (Peterson, 1999). The conventions also aim to address the disparities between males and females, and to challenge those normative political and socio-cultural structures that create inequality and ignore gender equity (UN ECOSOC, 1997). In Zimbabwe, the domestic institutional frameworks for gender equality and mainstreaming in politics in the form of the constitution and the National Gender Policy are guided and/or informed by this global and/or regional architecture on gender equality. As such, specific attention will be paid to the provisions of the Constitution of Zimbabwe and the National Gender Policy as they are the core guiding documents of the gender mainstreaming initiatives in the country.

The Constitution of Zimbabwe

The Constitution of Zimbabwe makes a firm commitment to gender equality. It calls for gender mainstreaming and Chapter 2 Article 17 (1) indicates that the State must promote full gender balance in the Zimbabwean society, and in particular, the State must provide for the full participation of women in all spheres of the Zimbabwean society on the basis of equality with men (Government of Zimbabwe, 2013). Furthermore, it states that:

The State must take all measures needed, including legislative measures, to ensure that both genders are equally represented in all institutions and agencies of government at every level; and women constitute at least half the membership of all Commissions and other elective and appointed governmental bodies established by or under the Constitution or any Act of Parliament; and the State and all institutions and agencies of government at every level must take practical measures to ensure that women have access to resources, including land, on the basis of equality with men; and the State must take positive measures to rectify gender discrimination and imbalances

resulting from past practices and policies (Government of Zimbabwe, 2013:20).

Moreover, the Constitution, on Rights of Women, posits that every woman has full and equal dignity of the person with men and this includes equal opportunities in political, economic and social activities (Government of Zimbabwe, 2013). Notably, the country is dedicated to upholding gender equality and pursuing gender mainstreaming in a bid to attain to a fair society where all citizens enjoy equality of opportunities and participation in all sectors.

The national gender policy

Zimbabwe has adopted a second National Gender Policy (NGP) which replaces the first National Gender Policy of 2004. According to the Ministry of Women Affairs, Gender and Community Development (MoWGCD, 2013: iv):

The first National Gender Policy gave way to a range of initiatives meant to address gender inequalities; and was underpinned by the ethos of Growth with Equity which was implemented under four thematic areas namely – (i) Women in Politics and Decision Making; (ii) Women and the Economy; (iii) Education and Training of Women; and (iv) Institutional Mechanisms for the Advancement of Women.

The second NGP “seeks to address the shortcomings of the 2004 NGP and the emerging issues prevailing under the changing political, economic and social contexts at local, regional and global levels” (MoWGCD, 2013: iv). According to the MoWGCD:

Some of the key developments post 2004 that set out new priorities include: (i) the 2005 Beijing global review that made recommendations to areas that required special attention and action; (ii) the submission of the combined State Party CEDAW Report; (iii) the development a national follow-up plan on Rio, and (iv) the 2008 SADC Protocol on Gender and Development that set out 28 substantive targets for achieving gender equality by 2015(MoWGCD, 2013: iv).

Notably, the aforementioned developments and other national priorities have repercussions on gender equality making a new NGP imperative for the effective advancement of gender equality and equity. Thus, the second NGP seeks:

...to achieve a gender just society where men and women enjoy equality and equity and participate as equal partners in the development processes of the country. The policy goal is to eradicate gender discrimination and inequalities in all spheres of life and development (MoWGCD, 2013: iv-v).

A number of priority areas were identified which are the basis for the development of the policy objectives and strategies for the period of its effectiveness. These priority areas are Gender, Constitutional and Legal Rights; Gender and Economic Empowerment; Gender, Politics and Decision Making; Gender and Health; Gender, Education and Training; Gender Based Violence; Gender and Environment; and Gender, Media and ICTS (MoWGCD, 2013). This cursory appreciation of the institutional framework on which efforts to bring about gender equality and equity are built upon, point to a committed male dominated political establishment intent on transforming among other things women's political fortunes. However, as will be revealed in the later sections of the article there is a serious disconnect between theoretical commitment and the actual practices. Nonetheless, it is critical to first of all conceptually frame the discussion by exploring the concept of participation in detail so as to delimit the boundaries of the analysis.

Conceptualising Political Participation

Participation as an analytical concept has undergone a lot of transformation in the recent past. It has been applied in various developmental arenas such as political, social, economic and environmental discourses. This makes it very difficult to find a universally acceptable definition of the concept. According to

Lamprianou (2013) political participation pertains to the quintessential act of democratic citizenship. Various political theorists argue that it has become unquestionable that broad participation in the decision-making processes is prerequisite for proper democratic governance (Dahl, 1971, 1998; Pateman, 1970). Munroe (2002) defines political participation in terms of the extent to which citizens are exercising their constitutional right to engage in political activities. On the other hand Verba *et al.* (1995:38) perceive political participation as any “activity that has the intent of effect of influencing government actions either by directly affecting the making or implementation of public policy or indirectly by influencing the selection of people who make the policies”. While observations by Verba *et al.* (1978) are true that all individuals ought to have an equal opportunity to influence decision-making processes, studies have shown that women’s participation in formal political structures and processes is insignificant (Bari, 2005).

According to Arstein (1969) there are levels of participation ranging from manipulation at the bottom of the ladder to consultation in the middle of the ladder to citizen control at the apex. Buttod (1999) observes that there are different types of participation. Functional participation occurs when people take part in decision making processes and are likely to contribute to discussion. Active participation occurs when people contribute more or less directly to decision making process via negotiation procedures. Passive participation occurs when people are not involved in decision making processes but are merely informed of decisions. In the light of this conceptual framing of participation, the present study examines the conceptual and material bases of women’s exclusion from the mainstream political structures. Whilst the study recognises the broad nature of political participation and its multidimensionality it however restricts its

analysis to selected cases involving women involvement in the legislature and executive.

Women's Political Participation in Zimbabwe

This part of the article makes an exploration of the trajectories of women's participation in politics in post-colonial Zimbabwe over three historical periods, that is, the pre-GNU period; the inclusive government and the post-inclusive government periods. These historical periods encapsulate key political economy processes some of which could explain the changing fortunes of women in political and public policy spaces. During the first period (1980-2008) the country had just gained its independence and amongst other things instituted a new Ministry of Community Development and Women Affairs, faced instability in the form of state sponsored military persecution of mainly the Ndebele ethnic group in what is known as Gukurahundi, witnessed the signing of the Unity Accord between PF-ZAPU and ZANU-PF. More importantly, it was during this period that the first National Gender Policy (2004) was launched. From 2009 to 2013 Zimbabwe was governed by an inclusive government constituted by ZANU-PF and the two Movement for Democratic Change formations. The formation of the inclusive government involved a lot of political gamesmanship and negotiations and it is of interest to examine how these affected the position of women in the country's political processes. In 2013 ZANU-PF regained its parliamentary majority and by extension its sole mandate to govern the country. However, the triumph over opposition political parties coupled with a looming elective congress led to a lot of infighting in ZANU-PF which affected women as well.

The pre-GNU period (1980-2008)

In the period under review, the Zimbabwean parliamentary system was partly bicameral from 1980-1989 and from 2005 to present. Under this system there was both a lower and upper house. However, between 1990 and 2004 the country opted for a unicameral parliamentary system. In terms of gender distribution of seats in the respective Houses, tables 1 and 2 provide a summary:

Table 1: Gendered Composition of Zimbabwe House of Assembly (1980-2005)

Elections and Appointments	Seats	Men	Women	% of women
1980-84	100	91	9	9
1985-1990	100	92	8	8
1990	150	133	17	11.3
1995	150	129	21	14
2000	150	136	14	9.3
2005	150	126	24	16

(Sources: Parliament of Zimbabwe (undated) and Gaidzanwa (2004))

Table 2: Gendered Composition of Zimbabwe Senate (1980-1989; 2005-2008)

Elections and Appointments	Seats	Men	Women	% of women
1980	40	37	3	7.5
1985	40	37	3	7.5
2005	66	42	24	36.36

(Sources: Parliament of Zimbabwe (undated) and Gaidzanwa (2004))

Tables 1 and 2 provide evidence that in spite of the demographic reality that women have always been marginally more than men in numeric terms, women representation in both

Houses of Parliament has always been very low. An interesting dimension to the few women Members of Parliament (MPs) in the first decade of Zimbabwean independence is that most of them were linked to male figures or were veterans of the liberation struggle. For instance in the 1980 and 1985 general elections some of the female MPs were Julia Zvobgo wife to Edison Zvobgo a senior Zimbabwe African National Union-Patriotic Front (ZANU-PF) official; Joice Mujuru wife to the first black post-independence General of the Zimbabwe National army; Sabina Mugabe sister to the then Prime Minister of Zimbabwe, Robert Mugabe and Ruth Chinamano, wife to Josiah Chinamano, the deputy president in the Patriotic Front-Zimbabwe African People's Union (PF-ZAPU) political party. Even at the executive level, two of the three women who were either Ministers or Deputy Ministers were somehow linked to powerful male figures. Joice Mujuru became the first Minister of Youth, Sport and Recreation in Mugabe's 23-member cabinet, while Victoria Chitepo served as deputy Education and Culture minister and Naomi Nhwatiwa deputy minister of Post and Telecommunications (Zaba and Ndebele, 2013). Mujuru and Chitepo were relatives of politically powerful male figures, that is, Solomon Mujuru and Herbert Chitepo respectively. Herbert Chitepo was at one point the leader of ZANU-PF. These appointments reflect that the political arena becomes an extension of expressive roles that women are accustomed to in the domestic sphere and are identified through their more illustrious male partners. This trend is even discernible where the conferment of hero/heroine status is concerned. Goredema and Chigora (2009) make a compelling argument that the heroines that lie at the National heroes acre are there largely on the strengths of their husbands' political power rather than their own.

In terms of appointments to government, Steady (1986) argues that women are assigned soft positions. These positions include

controlling portfolios on women's affairs, sports, youth, social welfare, and small businesses amongst others. It is thus not surprising that women did not and have not as yet assumed ministerial positions in portfolios such as Finance, Defence, Foreign Affairs and National Security amongst others. As such one is bound to question the government's commitment to gender equality and equity. The Zimbabwean situation is unlike that of South Africa where in its short post-apartheid history women have on a number of occasions assumed influential portfolios such as those of Defence, Foreign Affairs, International Relations, Speaker of the House of Assembly, Speaker of the National Council of Provinces and the Deputy Presidency amongst others.

Another case worth reflecting on is that of Margaret Dongo who in 1990 became an MP with the backing of the National War Veterans Association of Zimbabwe. During her tenure as MP she was outspoken particularly on democracy, human rights, and for the marginalised groups in Zimbabwe. Her website claims because of her willingness to challenge the ZANU-PF leadership on these issues, she was deselected in the 1995 election for the Harare South Constituency (Dongo, Undated). She thus fought it out with the official ZANU-PF candidate Vivian Mwashita. The stakes were heavily staked against her as Matikinye (2005) observes that:

Even when men schemed to oust her through unorthodox means by pitting her against Vivian Mwashita, Dongo fought back tenaciously and recovered a constituency she had been robbed of by a female candidate who had "won" it through male connivance. She went on to lead the Zimbabwe Union of Democrats, breaking new ground by becoming the first ever woman in post-Independent Zimbabwe to lead a political party.

Dongo's case points to the hazards that women who seek to be independent-minded in politics face. This is attested by Giesler (2004:173) who notes "that ambitious and outspoken women

politicians have to deal with powerful male gatekeepers who favour the women's league type of women politician and they work to block the career advancement of women considered deviating from this ideal". To demonstrate that women were aware of their unfavourable position in politics, in August 1999, the ZANU-PF Women's league in its Victoria Falls meeting threatened to boycott the 1999 Party Congress if one of theirs was not to be part of the Party Presidium. One of the ZANU-PF MPs Mavis Chidzonga is quoted as having said "If nothing drastically changes at this congress, women will continue to be window dressers. Women have always been recognised as those who mobilise votes, produce children and sing praise songs for the men" (quoted in Machipisa, 1999). To further buttress men's chauvinistic attitudes towards women politicians, Chidzonga goes on to say:

The men are very comfortable to have an all bull team. Their attitude since we made the resolution in Victoria Falls has been so bad. Even as we lobby them, some are getting so extreme. They are used to a women's league that was passive and all it did was praise and sing for them. Now unfortunately, they have a different women's league. We have graduates among our members (quoted in Machipisa, 1999).

Regrettably for women, their demands came to naught as an all-male Presidium emerged at the Congress comprising of President Mugabe, Vice Presidents Simon Muzenda and Joseph Msika and Chairman John Nkomo. However, it is interesting to note that Mugabe is said to have preferred Thenjiwe Lesabe, the Women's League Chair for the Vice Presidency post (Matyszak, 2014). Political developments in the years 2004 and 2005 provide further impetus to the argument that males use statecraft on women to further their political ends. Having initially failed to bow down to the Women's league ultimatum in the run-up to the 1999 Congress it is interesting to note that women were requested to re-activate their demand prior to the 2004 ZANU-PF

Congress. Matyszak (2004) argues that this was at the instigation of President Mugabe working in cahoots with the Solomon Mujuru faction in ZANU-PF in order to counter the then Legal Affairs Secretary's (Emmerson Mnangagwa) plans to ascend to the Vice Presidency position following the death of the incumbent, Simon Muzenda. Mnangagwa had already secured the backing of the majority of the party's provinces (Matyszak, 2014; Moyo, 2004). Of interest is that the two dominant factions within ZANU-PF, that is, the Mujuru and Mnangagwa factions and President Mugabe all used women to further their political ends. The Mujuru faction with the support of the President lobbied for constitutional changes, one of which had the effect of guaranteeing a woman a place in the Presidium. From the Mujuru side this move effectively meant counterchecking Mnangagwa's ambitions. It was viewed as expedient for the leader of the party to appoint Joice Mujuru to that position at that point in the country's history. She belonged to the right political camp. She did not pose a threat to the party leader and was therefore a safe bet for him. Misihairabwi and Kwinje (2005) explained this political manoeuvre:

It must first be understood that Mujuru is only acceptable to Mugabe as his Vice President because she does not threaten his hold on power, either nationally or within the ruling party. She has been propelled to the party's top most position precisely because she poses no threat to any of the distinct factions engaged in a bitter power struggle within ZANU-PF.

For the Mnangagwa faction their 'pawn' in the political gamesmanship was Thenjiwe Lesabe whom they forwarded as a candidate to counteract Joice Mujuru's candidacy mostly because of her two 'marketable' demographic traits at that point in time, that is, her sex (female) and ethnicity (Ndebele). In 2005 the Government of Zimbabwe passed Constitutional Amendment number 17 which had a number of regressive provisions. Amongst some of these provisions, this constitutional

amendment sought to re-introduce the senate in a climate of a tight fiscal space and the addition of further restrictions on freedom of movement. Most segments of society including women were against this amendment. To sweeten the amendment and probably to gain the support of women, gender sensitive provisions were added on to section 23 which dealt on issues of equality by adding further grounds for “non-discrimination to include sex, marriage and disability” (Genderlinks, 2012). Furthermore, as part of concessions to win the hearts and minds of women, ZANU-PF adopted and implemented a quota system for candidates for the National Assembly in 2005 under the guise of adhering to the SADC Principles and Guidelines on the conduct of democratic elections and to the SADC Declaration on gender and development which stipulated 30% seats for women by the year 2005. However, at least a third of women who were nominated were nominated “in opposition strongholds where they had little chances of success and in the end only 17.7% of elected ZANU-PF members were women” (Chiroro, 2005:102; see also Ndoro, 2005). Even during the primary election process there was evidence that in some instances the quota system was being used to settle political scores. The most cited of these examples is that of the Tsholotsho constituency where the then incumbent MP, Jonathan Moyo’s application to stand on a ZANU-PF ticket was rejected under the guise that the Constituency was reserved for a woman (Mail and Guardian, 2005; Kabemba, 2005). Noteworthy is that this trend was repeated in the 2008 elections where the opposition MDC also fielded 9 women in rural constituencies where it was not strong whereas ZANU-PF fielded 10 in urban areas (Makamure, 2008).

The GNU era: 2009 - 2013

In 2009, Zimbabwe witnessed the formation of a GNU. Dziva *et al.* (2013:83) posit that this was “to end the political and economic impasse in the country as well as a foundation towards a new constitutional dispensation” and it ended on the 29th of June 2013. Dodo *et al.* (2012) note that this was meant to ease the antagonisms between and among the political parties and to rescue the deteriorating protracted political and economic crises that began in 2000. The basis of the coalition government was the assumption that equitable participation by all prominent political parties (in the civil service, cabinet, diplomatic posts, the judiciary, army, police and the intelligence service) would diminish the potential for conflict and enhance prospects for national stability, integration and development (Dodo *et al.*, 2012).

The preamble of the Global Political Agreement (GPA) document states that there was need for gender parity, particularly the need to appoint women to strategic cabinet posts (IDASA, 2011). Even the three principals in the unity government, namely President Robert Mugabe, the Prime Minister Morgan Tsvangirai and Deputy Prime Minister Arthur Mutambara concurred on the importance of respecting a woman and according her equal rights (MoWGCD, 2011). It is however unfortunate that the participation of women at the negotiation stage was limited. Out of the 6 negotiators only one was a woman (Priscilla Misihairabwi-Mushonga) seconded by the Movement of Democratic Change then led by Arthur Mutambara. Although the MoWGCD (2013) notes significant milestones in addressing gender disparities and in some cases gender parity, most critics argue otherwise, especially looking at the GNU era. Banda and Masuka (2013:57) note that:

Despite all the verbal and documentary expression of intention on the part of the country's leadership, the reality on the ground points in a totally different direction, with women seemingly having been systematically side-

lined from key political processes that have taken place throughout the history of the country.

According to Shaba (2011:154), “under the inclusive Government... women occupied 8 of the 50 Cabinet posts (16%); 30 of the 210 seats in Parliament (14%); and 20 of the 60 seats in the Senate (33%)”. Moreover, they “jointly constituted 17.9 % in both the Senate and the House of Assembly, consequently, lowering women's influence in decision making on pertinent issues affecting the nation” (Nyemba and Muzavazi, 2013:108). Banda and Masuka (2013:69) posit that:

... in the actual implementation only three women can be safely said to have been in strategic posts; and these are Vice President (Joice Mujuru), Deputy Prime Minister (Thokozani Khupe) and Home Affairs Co-Minister (Theresa Makone). However, despite their low representation, the appointment of a woman as president of the Senate and another as the Deputy Speaker of Parliament is a positive move to ensure gender parity in prominent positions in parliament.

This shows the perpetual culture in Zimbabwe where “women’s participation in Zimbabwe's parliament has been marginal since independence in 1980 and the GPA inherited a decrease in the number of women parliamentarians due to political violence which minimised their involvement in the harmonised elections of 2008” (Nyemba and Muzavazi, 2013:108), causing marginal changes to be celebrated victories. The GPA therefore made no tangible attempts to deal with the myriad issues that perpetually limit the participation of women in political decision-making processes in Zimbabwe (Shaba, 2011). It “consistently spoke to the ideals of equality, fairness, justice and non-discrimination, yet there was an absence of political will to follow through on these ideals” (Mangezvo, 2013:76). Paul Mangwana the then Constitution Parliamentary Select Committee (COPAC) co-chairperson during an address with journalists in Mutare in 2012 stated that ‘the women always complain that

political parties are male-dominated and that they want to have more seats allocated to them, but they can just form a political party of their own and have 100% candidates in all constituencies' (quoted in Mhlanga, 2014). This sarcastic utterance is a mere reflection of the prevalent patriarchal hegemonies that perpetuate chauvinistic patterns in present day politics regarding the question of gender equality. It is clear therefore that "the marginalization of women under the GPA was not an accident, but rather a continuation of a process that was already entrenched in Zimbabwe's political system" (Banda and Masuka, 2013:56).

During the GNU, very little was done about the issue of gender inequality in all dimensions. In essence, the principal parties to the arrangement departed from their declared commitment to channel their collective energies towards creating a genuine, viable, permanent, sustainable and nationally acceptable solution to the Zimbabwe situation, (including the seclusion of women and upholding gender mainstreaming initiatives), but rather focused instead on positioning themselves for the next elections (Mangezvo, 2013). This has been demonstrated by the glaring low numbers of women in political positions compared to men. These "culturally-informed anxieties about women generally, and their role and place in governance particularly, continue in Zimbabwe today as a result of which women remain relegated to the margins of the economy and governance" (Mangezvo, 2013). The binding gender policy that was in place during this period, with very powerful messages on the need to recognize women in land allocation, education and training, and health had no clear funding plans for the pronouncements, hence leaving them open to speculation' (Mangezvo, 2013). It is prudent therefore that an analysis of the post GNU era be made to either firm up the foregoing or discard in light of the realities that characterised the period in terms of Zimbabwean women's participation in politics.

Post GNU period: July 2013 to present

The year 2013 brought about two major paradigm shifts in the Zimbabwean political landscape. Firstly, the year saw the drafting and the resounding “YES” vote for the new home grown constitution which replaced the 1979 Lancaster House constitution. The second major shift was the ruling party’s landslide victory in the July 31 harmonised election. ZANU-PF amassed well over the two thirds majority to form a government with the privilege of amending the Constitution. This was a major shift from the general composition of the Legislature since the emergence of the MDC party in 1999. The landslide victory therefore gave the incumbent president the power to name his cabinet guided by the new constitution of 2013. However, in September 2013 the President appointed his 26 member cabinet consisting of only three women. He also appointed three women out of 13 ministers of state, 10 of which are provincial affairs ministers and the other 3 servicing the presidium. Amongst 24 deputy ministers, only 5 are women. A total of 60 women were elected to the National Assembly in accordance with the Constitution through proportional representation. This was contrary to the stipulations of the Zimbabwean constitution and the SADC Protocol on Gender and Development ratified by the 7th Parliament in October 2009. The three women represented a mere 12% of the cabinet, which was a far cry from the expected 50-50 representation based on sex and well below women’s proportional share in view of the fact that they constitute 52% of the population recorded in the 2012 population census.

In defence of his decision, the President was quoted by media as saying: “Give us the women. This time we did proportional representation; there were just not enough women. Women are few in universities. It’s no longer necessary to do affirmative action. It’s free for all” (quoted in Zaba and Ndebele, 2013). The President’s decision and defence drew a lot of outcry from the

Zimbabwean populace in general and women in particular. Many questions were asked as to the respect of the new constitution and with regards to which women the President was making reference to. How could it be possible that out of 52% women population, only three were educated enough to take cabinet posts? Yet many Zimbabwean women are the holders of Master's and Doctoral degrees and are finding jobs all over the world. The President's stance led many to question if the Zimbabwean women referred to were just ZANU-PF women and not necessarily the generality of Zimbabwean women. The President is mandated by the constitution of Zimbabwe to appoint five ministers outside parliament to bring in technocrats and to cater for special interest groups. The feeling with many women was that the President could have used these provisions to appoint women technocrats. However, the President appointed only male ministers to fill these posts. Most of these men had lost in the party primary elections. It is interesting to note that an MP for Buhera South Constituency who belongs to the President's ruling party and was said to be interested in the Lands ministry was quoted as saying:

It doesn't matter whether I went to school or not, I learnt how to hold a gun without going to school. What does being an MP or a minister has to do with going to school? I don't care which committee I will be in. (quoted in *Zimeye.com*, 2013)

According to Masunungure (2013):

It is not a question of being educated but that most educated women are not excited by politics or they fear participation in politics. Also there are cultural constraints where women find it difficult to attend meetings in the evening (quoted in Zaba and Ndebele, 2013)

This means that the gender roles are still constraining women to take up positions in politics and that politics in Zimbabwe is still male dominated. The President has called upon women to put more effort in their campaigns in order to do well in politics.

However research has shown that women have been disadvantaged for so many years that they are unable to compete with men. According to Zungura and Nyemba (2013:205):

Politics these days is about what the aspiring Member of Parliament gives to the voters which might be beer or monies for projects. Women are poor hence the need to support them financially especially during election time if an increased participation of women in politics is to be realised.

This implies that even if women may wish to participate as suggested by the President, they do not have the financial clout that men do hence they are out-competed. In contrast, South Africa and Rwanda have done well in terms of women representation in parliament and other decision making positions. South Africa's 25-member cabinet has 13 female ministers and 16 female deputy ministers. The majority of provinces are governed by women as five out of nine premiers in the country are women. The deliberate gender equality policies have seen an increased number of South African women holding influential positions in international organisations. A case in point is that of Nkosazana Dlamini-Zuma, the current chairperson of the African Union Commission. Rwanda is ranked first in the world for having the highest number of women in Parliament. Females constitute 56,5% of Rwanda's National Assembly and 38,5% of its Senate (IPU, 2015). The achievement by the above mentioned countries necessitates the need to unpack the utility of proportional representation in the Zimbabwean context. Zimbabwe's constitution, as mentioned above, provides for proportional representation especially in Senate. According to Chapter 6 (4) 120 (2) of the constitution of Zimbabwe, Senators must be elected under a party-list system of proportional representation and male and female candidates are supposed to be listed alternately, every list being headed by a female candidate (Government of Zimbabwe, 2013).

However despite this provision, the Senate is still dominated by men owing to the 16 seats that are reserved for the traditional chiefs who are predominantly male. The 60 National Assembly seats which are set aside to increase women participation in politics have seen the appointed members of parliament being ridiculed by those who were elected directly. The Members of Parliament on proportional representation ticket are referred to as BACCOSI² MPs, because they were not directly elected but politically appointed. As argued by Clayton *et al.* (2014), the ability of quotas to increase women's physical presence in legislative bodies does not give the recipients the ability to shape these bodies in the same manner as their non-quota colleagues. They further argue that quota system recipients need to be recognised and respected. Zungura and Nyembe (2013) posit that affording women the ability to participate through the quota system without them accessing political resources may not be enough to transform the patriarchal norms against women in politics. Accordingly, Nwankwor (2014) argues that political patronage and patriarchal networks that have excluded women from these bodies could continue to constrain their ability to substantively represent the interests of women once they secure the seats. This means that unless there are further reforms accompanying quota systems the status quo might continue.

The political events of the year 2014 adversely impacted on the stride that Zimbabwe had made in the previous decades to bring about gender balance in the political landscape. The ruling ZANU-PF party usurped the powers of the country's first female vice president over allegations she planned a 'political coup' against the president. This signified the end of the ZANU-PF career of a woman who epitomised women's fledgling political influence. It also showed the world of the real gender gaps that

²BACCOSI stands for Basic Commodity Supply Side Intervention It was a programme that was initiated by the Reserve Bank of Zimbabwe at the height of economic meltdown in 2007-2009 where citizens were given groceries at a very low price to enable them to survive (*Newsday*, 2014).

the system had papered over. The talk of gender equality seems to be a mere rhetoric that the male-dominated Zimbabwean political leadership never believed in. Mujuru's crime was the alleged wish to replace the seating president. The extraordinary shifts of political power within the ruling party made women to appear more like pawns in a men's political chess game. To further buttress this argument, the immediate period prior and after the ZANU-PF 2014 congress has witnessed the meteoric rise of Grace Mugabe in the country's political landscape. However, like other women politicians before her, it can be argued that her political power is anchored on male power. On one hand she is riding on President Mugabe's interests of managing succession dynamics within ZANU-PF and in government. On the other hand there is the Generation 40 (G40) group which social commentators are claiming is using Grace to counter check the rise of the Vice President Emmerson Mnangagwa as they ready themselves to take over the control of the party and eventually the government³. Mujuru's alleged hunger for power led to the President to make the infamous remark regarding women and politics which is presented in the introductory section. The President's sentiments seemed to suggest that women should not aspire to be leaders. This view also demonstrated that all the rhetoric about gender equality in politics was a mere façade meant to lure women's vote but did not have the necessary political backing of male leaders. This further speaks of a deep entrenchment of a patriarchy within the Zimbabwean society. This is evidenced by comments attributed to President Mugabe when he said "I tell the women, as long as the man pays *lobola*, you cannot have equality with him" (*Newsday*, 2014). These observations are shared by Thata (2015) who observe that: This ZANU-PF government is patriarchal; you know how Mai Mujuru

³ See A. Magaisa online: <http://www.newzimbabwe.com/opinion-25282-Chaos+Theory+in+Zanu+PF+succession/opinion.aspx>.

See also <http://www.newsdezimbabwe.co.uk/2015/07/g40-positions-grace-for-power.html>

was ripped of her post as VP. This is evidence of how women are used, abused and dumped when they do not need those women anymore (quoted in *Zimeye.com*, 2015).

To buttress the above observations, the media reported that the Spirit mediums, allegedly working with war veterans and military big wigs linked to one of the ZANU-PF factions, also waded into Zimbabwean politics by organising a *bira*. A *bira* is a Shona religious ritual conducted by the spirit mediums. According to *Newsday* (2014), there were “plans that the three leading spirit mediums would declare that the ancestral spirits have refused to have Zimbabwe run by a female President”. The main idea was to block Mujuru from aspiring to be the president of Zimbabwe:

After such declaration, the war veterans would go to provinces telling people they should not support Vice-President Joice Mujuru because spirit mediums have warned against a female leader. “The spirit mediums would also say that any woman who dares to take over power would be killed by the spirits” (*Newsday*, 2014).

While men can be fingered in the demise of the former Vice President, of particular interest is that her persecution was fronted and orchestrated by women with Grace Mugabe and Oppah Muchinguri leading the attack. According to Thata (2015) the women who led the Mujuru purge were serving the patriarchal structures of our societies. Thus Chitsike (2015) argues that, while women are oppressed by culture, male attitudes and behaviours as well as political structures and processes, they are also their own enemy. Chitsike (2015) notes that women suffer from a “pull her down syndrome” (PhD) in the sense that they do not support each other to hold leadership positions. Chitsike posits that the reason why women sell each other out is seldom for their political affiliation but the “PHD” syndrome disguised as politics.

Conclusion

This article has reflected on women's participation in Zimbabwe's political processes. The assessment has revealed that whilst there have been some moves towards gender equality, these have not resulted in gender equity. Furthermore, the existing mechanisms that attempt to bring about gender equality, such as quota systems are unlikely to have a sustainable impact on women's numeric representation in political processes. A number of cases cited revealed that women's fortunes in ascending the political ladder have in most cases always been linked to those of male figures. These could be husbands, brothers or other relations with political clout. Women enjoy these 'borrowed robes' in so far as their familial political backers control the levers of political power. In fact, in some cases the rise of women can be linked to their 'usage' as pawns by male political players to checkmate their male political rivalries. This is especially true where intra-party political tensions before major political contestations such as elective congresses are at their zenith. In such instances dominant male political players cede some ground to women through some cosmetic changes to the institutional terrain. However, such moves as has been demonstrated in a number of cases in this article, though compromising the direct interests of men founded on patriarchal values inadvertently reinforce patriarchy's stranglehold on power. The discussion has also revealed that those women who have dared to be independent of male control have been obliterated into political oblivion. Given the cases reviewed it is tempting to conclude that gender equity will remain a mirage for as long as the institution of patriarchy is still deeply entrenched in Zimbabwe's political processes and women allow men to manipulate them in exchange for short-term political and material gains. Thus, going by Arstein's (1969) levels of participation, evidence points to very low levels of women's political participation which manifest through their manipulation

by males. The political (mis)‘fortunes’ of Zimbabwean women in the last 35 years notwithstanding the theoretical calls for gender equality points to the success of male statecraft in continued domination of women in political processes. As such without confronting these realities the attainment of gender equity in political participation will remain a mirage.

References

- Arnstein, S.R. (1969). ‘A ladder of citizen participation’, in *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 35(4):216-224.
- Aviel, J. F. (1981). ‘Political participation of women in Latin America’, in *Political Research Quarterly*, 34 (1): 56-173.
- Banda, R. G. and Masuka, T. (2013). ‘An analysis of the marginalization of women in conflict resolution initiatives in Zimbabwe: The case of the Global Political Agreement’, in *Southern Peace Review Journal* 2(1):56-74.
- Bari, F. (2005). ‘Women’s political participation: Issues and challenges’. Available at: <http://www.un.org/womenwatch/daw/egm/enabling-environment2005/docs/EGM-WPD-EE-2005-EP.12%20%20draft%20F.pdf> (Accessed, 6 June 2015).
- Chiroro, B. (2005). ‘Persistent inequalities: Women and electoral politics in the Zimbabwe Elections in 2005’, in *Journal of African Elections*, 4(2):91-106.
- Chitsike, K. (2013). ‘Zim’s new cabinet: An open letter to Mr. R.G. Mugabe.’ Available at: <https://researchandadvocacyunit.wordpress.com/tag/women/> (Accessed, 10 June 2015).
- Chitsike, K. (2013). ‘Do you have the PHD syndrome?’ Available at: <http://www.researchandadvocacyunit.org/system/files/International%20Women's%20Day%20Brochure.pdf> (Accessed, 20 July 2015).

- Clayton, A. *et al.* (2014). 'Present without presence? Gender, quotas and debate recognition in the Ugandan parliament', in *Representation*, 50 (3): 379-392.
- Dahl, R. A. (1971). *Polyarchy: Participation and opposition*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Dahl, R. (1998). *On democracy*. New Haven: Yale University Press.
- Dodo, O. *et al.* (2012). 'Four years into Zimbabwe's Government of National Unity: Assessing the challenges and successes from the civil society's perspective', in *LWATI: A Journal of Contemporary Research*, 9(3):202-215.
- Dongo, M. (undated). 'Margaret Dongo'. Available at: <http://www.margaretdongo.com/bio-margaret-dongo/> (Accessed, 15 June 2015).
- Dube, T. (2013). 'Engendering politics and parliamentary representation in Zimbabwe', in *International Journal of Development and Sustainability*, 2(1):101-1024.
- Dziva, C. *et al.* (2013). 'A critique of the 2008 Government of National Unity and human rights protection in Zimbabwe', in *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention*, 2(8):83-92.
- Gaidzanwa, R. (2004). 'Gender, women and electoral politics in Zimbabwe', *EISA Research Report* No. 8. Johannesburg: EISA.
- Geisler, G. (2004). 'Women and the remaking of politics in Southern Africa: Negotiating autonomy, incorporation and representation.' Uppsala: Nordiska Afrikanstitutet.
- Genderlinks (2012). 'Women up the pressure in constitutional review'. Available at: <http://www.genderlinks.org.za/article/zimbabwe-women-up-the-pressure-in-constitutional-review-2012-10-11> (Accessed, 21 June 2015).
- Geisler, G. (2004) *Women and the re-making of politics in Southern Africa: Negotiating autonomy, incorporation and representation*. Uppsala: Nordiska Afrikainstitutet.

- Goredema, D. and Chigora, P. (2009) 'Fake heroines and the falsification of history in Zimbabwe 1980-2009', in *African Journal of History and Culture*, 1(5):76-83.
- Government of Zimbabwe (2013). *The Constitution of Zimbabwe Amendment No. 20*. Harare: Government of Zimbabwe.
- IDASA (2011). 'Gender analysis of Zimbabwe's Global Political Agreement'. Pretoria: IDASA and Feminist Institute of Southern Africa.
- IPU (2015). 'Women in national parliaments'. Available at: www.ipu.org/wmn-e/classif.htm. (Accessed, 17 July 2015).
- Kabemba, C. (2005). 'Nomination of candidates and the 2005 Zimbabwe parliamentary elections'. Available at: <http://www.content.eisa.org.za/pdf/et19.pdf> (Accessed, 17 July 2015).
- Kurebwa, J. (2014). 'Rural women's representation and participation in local governance in the Masvingo and Mashonaland central provinces of Zimbabwe', in *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 19 (2):125-132.
- Kwangwari, C. (2009). 'Formal politics at the district and sub-district levels: The case of Goromonzi'. (Unpublished MPhil thesis, Harare, University of Zimbabwe). Mail and Guardian (2005). 'Mugabe targets Zim's women voters'. Available at: <http://mg.co.za/article/2005-03-25-mugabe-targets-zims-women-voters> (Accessed, 12 July 2015).
- Laing, A. (2015). 'Robert Mugabe: 'Women can never be on a par with men'', *The Telegraph*, London, 30 January, 2015. Available at: <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/africaandindianocean/zimbabwe/11380108/Robert-Mugabe-Women-can-never-be-on-a-par-with-men.html> (Accessed, 12 July 2015).
- Lamprianou, I. (2013). 'Contemporary political participation research: A critical assessment', in Demetriou, K. (ed.). *Democracy in transition: Political participation in the European Union*. Berlin: Springer.

- Machipisa, L. (1999). 'Zimbabwe: Women excluded from top posts in ruling party'. Available at: <http://www.ipsnews.net/1999/12/politics-zimbabwe-women-excluded-from-top-posts-in-ruling-party/> (Accessed, 15 July 2015).
- Makamure, L. (2008). 'Women surpass 30% quota'. Available at: <https://www.theindependent.co.zw/2008/02/28/women-surpass-30-quota/> (Accessed, 20 July 2015)
- Mangezvo, P. L. (2013). 'Debating the Global Political Agreement and gender equality in Zimbabwe: A critical analysis of women's access to land ownership and political decision making', in *Southern Peace Review Journal*, 2(1):75-96.
- Matenga, M. (2013). 'Triumphant Chinotimba eyes lands ministry', *NewsDay*, Harare, 16 August 2013. Available at: <https://www.newsday.co.zw/2013/08/16/triumphant-chinotimba-eyes-lands-ministry/> (Accessed, 17 July 2013).
- Mhlanga, B. (2014). 'Violence, social inequalities force women out of politics', Available at: <https://www.newsday.co.zw/2014/09/19/violence-social-inequalities-force-women-politics/>, (Accessed, 14 July 2015)
- Ministry of Women Affairs, Gender and Community Development (2011). *Let`s go 50/50: Stop gender based violence*. Harare: Ministry of Women Affairs, Gender and Community Development.
- Ministry of Women Affairs, Gender and Community Development (2013). *The national gender policy (2013-2017)*. Harare: Ministry of Women Affairs, Gender and Community Development.
- Misihairabwi, P. and Kwinje, G. (2005). 'ZANU PF's latest gimmick: Women'. Available at: <http://archive.kubatana.net/html/archive/opin/050213pmsgk.asp?sector=WOMEN> (Accessed, 10 July 2015).
- Moyo, J. (2004). 'Tsholotsho saga: The untold story'. Available at:

- <http://www.thestandard.co.zw/2004/12/17/tsbolotsbo-saga-the-untold-story-3/> (Accessed, 16 July 2015).
- Munroe, T. (2002). *An introduction to politics: Lectures for first-year students*. Kingston: Canoe Press.
- Mushaya, E. (2014). 'Spirit mediums wade into ZANU fights'. *NewsDay*, Harare, 10 September, 2014, Available at: <https://www.newsday.co.zw/2014/09/10/spirit-mediums-wade-zanu-pf-fights/> (Accessed, 15 July 2015).
- Muzulu, P. (2014). 'Mugabe under fire', *NewsDay*, Harare, 4 December 2014.
- Ndoro, C. 2005: 'Zimbabwe: Election administration and constitutional and legal framework for the 2005 parliamentary elections'. *Zimbabwe Update, No.1*. Johannesburg: EISA
- Nhongo-Simbanegavi, J. (2000). *For better or worse*. Harare: Weaver Press.
- Nyemba, E. Z. and Muzavazi, F. (2013). 'The effects of the Global Political Agreement on women's participation in Zimbabwean politics', in *Southern Peace Review Journal*, 2(1):97-117.
- Nwankwor, C. (2015). 'Women cabinet ministers' role in gender equality'. *Zimbabwe Independent*, Harare, 10 January 2014. Available at: www.theindependent.co.zw/2014/01/10/ (Accessed, 22 June 2015).
- Parliament of Zimbabwe (Undated). 'Gender disaggregated data in the Parliament of Zimbabwe since 1980'. Available at: http://www.parlzim.gov.zw/attachments/article/46/History_of_Women_Parliamentarians.pdf (Accessed, 5 July 2015).
- Pateman, C. (1970). *Participation and democratic theory*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Reuters (2014). 'Robert Mugabe accuses Joice Mujuru of plot to unseat him'. *The Telegraph*, London, 3 December, 2014. Available at: <http://www.telegraph.co.uk/news/worldnews/africaandindianocean/zimbabwe/11270202/Robert-Mugabe->

- accuses-Joice-Mujuru-of-plot-to-unseat-him.html (Accessed, 6 June 2015).
- SADC (2008). 'SADC protocol on gender and development'. Available at: http://www.sadc.int/files/8713/5292/8364/Protocol_on_Gender_and_Development_2008.pdf (Accessed, 22 June, 2015).
- Shaba, L. (2011). 'Dreaming of equality: Time to fulfil the GPA's promises to women'. Available at: <http://www.osisa.org/book/export/html/2547> (Accessed, 14 July 2015).
- Shvedova, N. (undated). 'Obstacles to women's participation in parliament', in Ballington, J. and Karam, A. (eds.). *Women in parliament: Beyond numbers, a revised edition*. Stockholm: International IDEA.
- Thata, N. (2015). 'A second letter to all women in Zimbabwe in preparation for the grand boycott! "Passive resistance'. Available at: www.zimeye.com/international-women-day-8th-march-2015/#sthash.eCziHOHW.dpuf (Accessed, 17 July 2015).
- UNDP (United Nations Development Programme) (2005). *Human Development Report 2005: International Cooperation at a Crossroads - Aid, Trade and Security in an Unequal World*. New York: UNDP.
- United Nations. (1948). 'The Universal Declaration of human rights'. Available at: <http://www.un.org/en/documents/udhr/> (Accessed, 9 July 2015).
- United Nations Economic Commission for Africa. (2012). 'Africa women's rights observatory'. Available at: http://www1.uneca.org/awro/awro_Thematic.aspx (Accessed, 9 July 2015).
- UN ECOSOC (1997). *Mainstreaming the gender perspective into all policies and programmes in the United Nations system*. New York: UNECOSOC.
- Verba, S. et al. (1978). *Participation and political equality: A seven-nation comparison*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Verba, S. *et al.* (1995). *Voice and equality: Civic voluntarism in American politics*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press.
- Zaba, F. and Ndebele, H. (2013). 'Outrage over cabinet gender bias'. *Zimbabwe Independent*, Harare, 20 September, 2013. Available at: <http://www.theindependent.co.zw/2013/09/20/outrage-cabinet-gender-bias/> (Accessed, 12 July 2015).
- Zimeye (2013). 'Zimbabwe: Fury as Mugabe assaults women'. Available at: <http://www.zimeye.com/fury-as-mugabe-assaults-women/> (Accessed, 17 July 2015).
- Zungura, M. and Nyemba, E. (2013). 'The implications of the quota system in promoting gender equality in Zimbabwean politics', in *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 3(2):204-212.